

Mechanisms of endolymphatic hydrops and cochlear synaptopathy after blast trauma

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Abstract. Hearing loss occurs after blast exposure. The classical explanation is hair cell death resulting from stereociliary bundle damage. Another cause is excess glutamate release, which leads to cochlear synaptopathy, which affects neural encoding at higher sound intensities. Additionally, endolymphatic hydrops (ELH), which is associated with hearing loss in Meniere's disease, also occurs after blast exposure and may contribute to hearing loss. Previously, we found that ELH was correlated with cochlear synaptopathy, and application of hypertonic saline to draw H₂O out of the endolymph treated ELH and reduced synaptic loss. This raised the possibility that ELH contributes to the development of cochlear synaptopathy. Here, we sought to determine if ELH causes cochlear synaptopathy. We studied wild type (CBACaJ) mice, those without stereociliary bundle stimulation (*Tecta*^{C1509G/C1509G}), and mice lacking hair cell glutamate release (Vglut3^{KO}). We used optical coherence tomography to compare ELH after blast exposure versus hypotonic challenge to isolate ELH from synaptopathy and derive the specific mechanisms at work. These findings were supported by histological sections and transmission electron microscopic imaging of dendritic terminals after blast trauma in wild type mice. We assessed whether glutamate excitotoxicity is necessary for ELH development after blast in Vglut3^{KO} mice. Three out of five Vglut3^{KO} mice lost all cochlear amplification and developed ELH, indicating that hair cell stimulation is necessary to develop ELH after blast trauma, but glutamate release is not. To determine if hair cells were involved in the development of ELH after hypotonic challenge, we applied a hypo-osmotic solution to the round window. ELH developed in wild type, *Tecta*^{C1509G/C1509G}, and Vglut3^{KO} mice, suggesting that ELH is due to an osmotic gradient between perilymph and endolymph, and neither hair cell transduction nor glutamate release are required. Next, we explored the relationship between ELH and synaptopathy. After blast exposure, only wild type, but not *Tecta*^{C1509G/C1509G} nor Vglut3^{KO} mice developed synaptopathy. These data show that stereociliary bundle stimulation is necessary for synaptopathy, but insufficient without glutamate release from the hair cell. Overall, our findings reveal that ELH simply reflects the osmotic load within endolymph, relative to perilymph, but is not a cause of synaptopathy.

INTRODUCTION

Blast exposure is known to cause structural and functional changes to the auditory system that are similar but more extreme than those found after noise exposure¹, and leads to, among other dysfunction, sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL). The classical explanation for SNHL after blast is trauma to the cochlear hair cells via their highly mechanosensitive hair bundles. Hair cell death occurs through a variety of pathways^{2,3} resulting in permanent hearing loss as evidenced by elevated auditory thresholds⁴. Another mechanism of noise-induced hearing loss that can occur without hair cell death is cochlear synaptopathy⁵. Either hair cell overstimulation after blast overpressure leads to excess release of the hair cell afferent neurotransmitter, glutamate, or extracellular ATP is released from other traumatized cells and activates Ca²⁺ channels^{6,7}. Both pathways result in the toxic entry of ions and water into synaptic boutons⁸⁻¹⁰ which damages the dendrite and produces synaptic ribbon loss in residual hair cells¹¹⁻¹³. Loss of auditory neurons does not necessarily elevate the threshold of hearing, but instead affects neural encoding at higher sound intensities, and thus has been called “hidden” hearing loss¹⁴. There are no effective treatments used clinically to prevent hearing loss via either mechanism after blast, or traumatic noise exposure.

After exposing mice to pressure waves approximating that of a roadside bomb in a specially designed blast chamber¹⁵, we used optical coherence tomography (OCT) to uncover endolymphatic hydrops (ELH) as an additional cochlear change that occurs post blast exposure¹⁶. ELH is thought to be caused by disruption of intracochlear fluid homeostasis that leads to excess endolymph accumulation in scala media, and is associated with hearing loss, possibly due to changes in cochlear mechanics^{1,17,18}. Our studies revealed that endolymphatic hydrops: 1) occurs after blast or noise trauma; 2) requires normal hair bundle stimulation; 3) is correlated with cochlear synaptopathy; 4) has a threshold level of noise identical to that needed to develop cochlear synaptopathy; and 5) along with synaptopathy can be treated by applying hypertonic saline to draw H₂O out of the endolymph^{1,16,19}. While these results support a correlative mechanism linking endolymphatic hydrops to cochlear synaptopathy, it raises the question of whether endolymphatic hydrops is a necessary step in the development of cochlear synaptopathy.

Here, we sought to determine whether endolymphatic hydrops causes cochlear synaptopathy. We hypothesized that ELH and synaptopathy are simply co-existent findings. To investigate our hypothesis, we compared wild type and transgenic mouse models that lack either hair cell stereociliary bundle stimulation (*Tecta*^{C1509G/C1509G})²⁰⁻²², or glutamate release (Vglut3^{KO})^{23,24}. We compared blast exposure versus hypotonic challenge, which we have previously shown causes hydrops without affecting cochlear tuning¹⁶. These findings were supported by specific ultrastructural changes detected by light and transmission electron micrographs (TEM) after blast trauma. Our data support the notion that ELH arises due to a disruption of hair bundle mechanotransduction after blast exposure, resulting in an osmotic gradient between perilymph and endolymph. Furthermore, ELH and cochlear synaptopathy reflect osmotic fluid shifts, but do not always co-exist.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

OCT imaging and vibrometry in mice

All procedures were approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee at the University of Southern California. Three strains of mice were used in these experiments (**Fig. 2A,B,C**): wild type (CBA/CaJ, JAX#: 000654); *Tecta*^{C1509G/C1509G} 22; and Vglut3^{KO} (JAX#: 016931) mice²⁴. All mice were 6–11 weeks old. We used our previously published custom-built OCT system²⁵⁻²⁷, which consists of a swept laser (Insight Photonic Solution, Inc. SLE-101; center wavelength=1310 nm, bandwidth=91 nm, sweep rate=100 kHz), a custom-built Mach-Zehnder interferometer, dual-balanced photodetector (Insight Photonic Solution, Inc., BPD-1), and digitizer (400 MS/s, Alazartech Inc. ATS9373). The axial resolution was ~12.5 μm (FWHM, refractive index = 1.4) and the lateral resolution was 9.8 μm.

Our surgical methods have been published²⁸. Briefly, after anesthetic induction, the skull was fixed to a custom head-holder, and left, or right bulla accessed. A fenestra allowed visualization of the otic capsule. We collected data from the apical turn, about a half-turn down from the helicotrema, where the characteristic frequency ranges from 7 – 11 kHz²⁵⁻²⁷. For the hypotonic challenge experiments, cochleae were imaged at 0, 30, and 60 min after initiation of hypotonic challenge. For blast experiments, cochleae were imaged 75 min – 6 h post blast. In a few animals (n=5-3), basilar membrane motion was recorded in response to sound. For these experiments, a probe with built-in speakers and microphone (ER10X, Etymotic Research) was sealed to the ear canal after pinna removal, and calibrated pure-tone stimuli were delivered.

Blast exposure and hypotonic challenge

Our custom-built blast chamber was used to deliver blast waves to anesthetized mice and our methods have been previously described¹⁵. In short, mice were exposed to a blast wave with peak pressures between ~130 kPa (196 dB SPL) and ~192 kPa (~200 dB SPL), and then either underwent surgery to expose the cochlea for OCT imaging, or the cochleae were harvested for structural analysis.

A hypotonic challenge was performed by applying distilled water (0 mOsm/kg) directly to the round window membrane and filling the middle ear after surgical exposure. This permitted osmosis to take place through this semipermeable membrane²⁹ into the cochlear perilymph. During this process, the mice were imaged *in vivo* using OCT. For a different set of mice, hypotonic challenge was administered via a myringotomy and this procedure is published¹⁶. Distilled water filled the middle ear space and covered the round window membrane for 5.5 h. The cochleae were collected for histological preparation and confocal imaging after 8 days. During all hypotonic challenge experiments, the distilled water was exchanged every 15-30 minutes to maintain an appropriate osmotic gradient. All images were analyzed for ELH using Fiji (NIH).

Histology and Microscopy

Our methods of histological preparation and immunofluorescence have been previously reported^{16,19}. Briefly, eight days after mice were exposed to a blast wave, hypotonic challenge, or no exposure, the mice were euthanized, cochleae extracted, and fixed (4% paraformaldehyde). We imaged presynaptic ribbons (anti-CtBP2, 1:200; BD Biosciences), postsynaptic densities (anti-Homer1, 1:800; Synaptic Systems), and hair cells (anti-Myosin VI, 1:100; Santa Cruz Biotechnology). Secondaries were Alexa Fluor 488 (1:500; Invitrogen, A-21151), Alexa Fluor 555 (1:500; Invitrogen, A-21428), and Alexa Fluor 647 (1:500; Invitrogen, A-21240). The tissues were mounted on glass slides using Fluoromount-G Mounting Medium with DAPI (Invitrogen, 00-4959-52).

Immunolabeled cochlear tissue slides were imaged using an inverted confocal microscope (Leica SP8). High resolution images were captured using a 63x objective (1.4 N.A.), with a z-step of 0.15 μm . The images were deconvolved in either Huygens Essential or Leica's Lightning software using the default deconvolution algorithm. Images were analyzed using Imaris software (Version 9.9, Oxford Instruments).

For TEM, cochleae from control or those exposed to a blast wave were isolated within 3 h post-blast and perfused with 1% OsFeCN and 1% Paraformaldehyde in 0.1M sodium cacodylate buffer through the oval window. The bulla was immersed in fixative (12 hours, 4 °C), rinsed in the buffer and shipped to Washington University in St Louis for further processing and imaging. In the Gratton lab, the cochlea underwent *en bloc* post-staining with 1% uranyl acetate (UA) and Walton's lead aspartate to enhance contrast. The cochleae were prepared for structural and ultrastructural analysis using an established protocol³⁰. Thick sections (1 μm) cut from the polymerized cochleae that had been bisected in the mid-modiolar plane were stained with 1% Toluidine Blue in 1% Borate. Images were examined and captured using a Nikon 80i microscope equipped with a Retiga EXi fast 1394 CCD camera and QCapture Pro software (Teledyne Photometrics). Thin sections (70 nm) of the upper basal turn (approx. 28-32 kHz) were mounted on copper hex grids and examined using a JEOL 1200 EX transmission electron microscope (JEOL USA Inc.) equipped with an AMT 8-megapixel digital camera and AMT Image Capture Engine V602 software (Advanced Microscopy Techniques, Woburn, MA). Final figures were assembled using Adobe Photoshop and Illustrator software (Adobe Systems).

RESULTS

Endolymphatic hydrops is due to an osmotic gradient between perilymph and endolymph

Previously, we showed that wild type mice develop endolymphatic hydrops after blast trauma disrupts mechanotransduction, but *Tecta*^{C1509G/C1509G} mice do not because their stereociliary bundles are not connected to the tectorial membrane and, thus, are not damaged by blast¹⁶. To validate this interpretation and determine whether synaptic glutamate release is involved in the development of ELH, we exposed *Vglut3*^{KO} mice to a blast wave (**Fig. 1**). Like wild type mice in our previous studies, *Vglut3*^{KO} mice developed ELH after blast exposure (**Fig. 1A, A'**). To quantify ELH, we calculated the SM/SV ratio (**Fig. 1A''**) and found it was significantly higher in blast exposed mice (**Fig. 1D**, $n = 5-7$, $p < 0.05$, unpaired t-test), despite the fact that two mice failed to develop ELH after blast exposure.

These results suggest that glutamate is not necessary to develop ELH. Additionally, in a subset of mice we recorded sound-induced vibrations from the basilar membrane. Similar to wild type mice, average sensitivity in control *Vglut3^{KO}* mice depended on both stimulus intensity and frequency, with a peak observed for the lowest sound intensities around the best frequency (BF) (**Fig. 1B**). After blast, however, responses became passive as seen by the lack of level dependence in the sensitivity curves (**Fig. 1B'**). Phase curves for both sets of animals were frequency dependent (**Fig. 1C, C'**). These results support the notion that the loss of mechanotransduction after blast leads to ELH. Because *Vglut3^{KO}* mice have normal stereocilia that are attached to the tectorial membrane, but do not release synaptic glutamate, these data support the notion that hair cell overstimulation via the hair bundle is necessary for developing endolymphatic hydrops after blast trauma, but glutamate is not.

Next, to determine whether creating an osmotic gradient across the cochlea causes ELH on its own, or if it requires hair cell function, we exposed the round

membrane to purified water, creating a hypotonic challenge to the cochlea that we have previously shown is sufficient to cause ELH¹⁶. Hypotonic challenge was applied to wild type, *Tecta^{C1509G/C1509G}*, and *Vglut3^{KO}* mice to test the role of mechanotransduction, and glutamate in the development of ELH (**Fig. 2**). We imaged the apical cochlea before (0 min), 30 and 60 mins after hypotonic challenge. Before hypotonic challenge, wild type and *Vglut3^{KO}* mice did not have ELH (**Fig. 2A',C',D,D''**), but on average *Tecta^{C1509G/C1509G}* mice had a mild case of endolymphatic hydrops (**Fig. 2B',D'**) that likely stems from the partial closure of transduction channels due to the lack of bias on the stereociliary bundles as they are not attached to the tectorial membrane²². OCT images show that ELH developed in all three genotypes after hypotonic challenge (**Fig. 2A''-C'''**). Analysis of the SM/SV ratio showed that it significantly increased 60 min after initiation of hypotonic challenge (**Fig. 2D-D''**, $n = 6-7$, $p < 0.05$, paired t-test). These findings argue that the position of Reissner's membrane is simply reflective of the osmotic load within the endolymph relative to the perilymph.

Ultrastructural changes occur rapidly after blast exposure

Previously, we found that blast trauma and cochlear synaptopathy were correlated, so we wanted to further explore the ultrastructural changes that occur in the cochlea after blast exposure. We harvested cochleae from wild-type mice within 3 h post blast. Light microscopic examination revealed changes in both the sensory and nonsensory epithelium (**Fig. 3A-D**). Our findings suggest fewer intracellular organelles within the inner hair cells (IHCs) and a loss of neuronal elements under IHCs immediately post-blast exposure. Interestingly, with the exception of the Boettcher cells, support cells in the organ of Corti and the external sulcus region showed a loss of intracellular organelles and cytoplasmic density. Electron micrographs were used to assess the ultrastructure of the hair cell – auditory nerve

dendrite region (Fig. 3E,F). Representative images illustrate swelling of dendritic terminals after blast exposure. Overall, trends show increased nerve fiber diameter with additional ultrastructural changes such as signs of metabolic stress noted by reduced cytoplasmic density of nerve fibers.

To further examine the mechanism underlying cochlear synaptopathy, wild type, *Tecta*^{C1509G/C1509G}, and *Vglut3*^{KO} mice were exposed to either hypotonic challenge, or a blast wave, and cochleas were harvested for confocal microscopy. Hair cells, presynaptic ribbons and postsynaptic densities were immunolabeled, and imaged. Compared to control ears, we found that hypotonic challenge did not affect the numbers of synapses in any mouse strain, even though this treatment led to ELH. Thus, as ELH and cochlear synaptopathy do not always coexist, ELH does not cause synaptopathy. Furthermore, blast did reduce the numbers of synapses in wild type mice as we have previously shown¹⁶, but it did not lead to a change in synapse numbers for either *Tecta*^{C1509G/C1509G} or *Vglut3*^{KO} mice. These data demonstrate that while stereociliary bundle stimulation is necessary for synaptopathy to occur following a blast wave, it is insufficient without IHC glutamate release. Collectively, our data suggest that ELH does not cause synaptopathy.

DISCUSSION

Our studies reveal that although endolymphatic hydrops and cochlear synaptopathy are both observed after blast exposure, endolymphatic hydrops does not cause synaptopathy. Both simply derive from the traumatic overstimulation of hair cell stereociliary bundles. Furthermore, our data argue that blast trauma does not directly alter the osmolarity of the intracochlear fluid compartment, rather hair cell involvement is necessary. A combination of transgenic mouse strains, and different imaging modalities allowed us to dissect this mechanism by selectively removing two key roles of hair cells, mechano-electrical transduction and synaptic transmission.

This work, in combination with data from other labs, has now created a reasonably clear description of the mechanistic steps that cause endolymphatic hydrops and cochlear synaptopathy after blast. However, we still need to understand if the ultrastructural changes to the organ of Corti remain long term, and what subtle effects they may have on cochlear mechanics once the damage to hair bundle mechanotransduction has healed. Substantial work must also be done to determine the best method and time frame for reducing the impact of both glutamate excitotoxicity, and osmotic balance shifts that lead to ELH. Finally, the cause of endolymphatic hydrops in Meniere's disease, a common disease that causes fluctuating hearing loss and vertigo, remains unknown, and while our data argue that changes in the osmotic balance between the endolymph and perilymph are at the root, it is unclear why this is occurring. These are questions that we should tackle and are critical for understanding how trauma affects cochlear mechanics and function.

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